

Check list before sampling

Make sure you have all the necessary equipment to carry out the sampling by going through the following list:

- Net with 20 μm mesh size complete with ballasted collector (Fig. 1)
- 2000 μm sieve
- 500 mL plastic bottle
- Graduated cylinder (100 mL)
- Sprayer
- Gloves
- Lamprey Filtration unit (Fig. 2)
- Membranes PC 10 μm \varnothing 47 mm (ref. TCTP04700 Millipore)
- Bleach (2,6% active chlorine dil. 10% in freshwater)
- 2 mL Bashingbead tubes (ref. S6012-50 Zymo Research) filled with 1 mL of DNA/RNA Shield (ref. R1100-50 Zymo Research)
- Lamprey wash bottle (Fig. 2, C) filled with filtered seawater (FSW)
- Logsheets to record all metadata

Check that all components of the sampling equipment are properly cleaned.

Plankton sampling (vertical tow)

1. Remove the net collector, shortly tow the net in the water in order to give a final rinse before starting the sampling.
2. Mount the collector, lower the net into seawater and let all the air out. Start releasing the pulling line down the right depth, and simultaneously record on the logsheet the GPS position and starting time.
3. Gently recover the pulling line, keeping it always under tension. As soon as the net is out of water, record ending time and depth on the logsheet.
4. Once out of the water, very carefully and abundantly rinse the walls of the net (from the outside of the net) with the sprayer filled with fresh seawater from the sampling site, and let all plankton particles fall into the collector. Pour out some of the collected liquid through the net mesh to adjust its level just below the collector's screw, otherwise part of the sample will overspill when unscrewing the collector with seawater from the sampling site to ensure a complete recovery of the sampled plankton.
5. Pour out the concentrated water sample from the collector on the 2000 μm sieve to collect the filtrate into the 500 mL bottle, measure its volume and register it on the logsheet.

Fig. 1 - Plankton sampling net. A) central stainless steel ring, B) entrance ring, C) Collector bucket.

Plankton concentration on filter membranes

1. Wear gloves and keep them on throughout the procedure.
2. Open the filter holder (A). Getting the support screen wet with FSW.

3. With clean tweezers (B) take a membrane out of the box (E) and place it on the filter holder, paying attention to keep the same orientation (the side that faces up in the box has to face up also on the support) and making sure that the filter lays flat (not folded) on it.
4. Close the filter holder, remove the top cover, gently shake the sampled suspension in the 500 mL bottle to ensure its homogeneity, and gradually pour it using the 100 mL graduated cylinder into the funnel. Turn on the peristaltic pump (I). Perform a step by step filtration of 100 mL aliquots, and stop whenever the filter membrane clogs. Record the volume of the sample poured into the funnel.

During filtration, check that there is no leakage from the connections or the filter holder.

5. When all the sample has gone through (or when the filter is saturated), rinse the graduated cylinder and then the tulip with the wash bottle filled with FSW (C), to recover plankton particles stucked on the walls.
6. When all the water has passed through, leave the pump running until the filter is dry.
7. Switch off the pump. Open the filter holder. Using the tweezers, carefully fold the filter and place it in a tube (F) containing beads and DNA/RNA shield solution. Invert the tube several times to impregnate the entire filter. Then, lower the tube quickly with a couple of swift movements of the arm from top to bottom, to get rid of air bubbles and make sure that the filter stays immersed in the buffer. Identify the tube and store the tube at -20°C for long time storage.

8. Clean the tweezers with bleach 10%, then water, before passing another filter.

Fig. 2 - Lamprey filtration system. A) Filter holder, B) Tweezers, C) Wash bottle, D) Silicone tubing, E) Membrane, F) Tube holder, G) Potentiometer, H) Lithium battery / Waterproof box, I) Peristaltic pump, J) Bleach tube.

Final cleaning

Rinse the whole equipment with freshwater, then fill the system with bleach 10%, wait 10 minutes, and empty the system. Finally rinse with distilled water and let it dry properly before storing it for the next sampling.

Identification sample

Sampling is done in duplicate, one sample send for sequencing, the other one for backup store at the laboratories. If possible, replicate from the same net if you have enough concentrated water, otherwise reproduce the sampling.

Stick the label barcode link to the logsheet, for the backup filter just report manually the number of the barcode.